

Opening of the new paths in Tashkent metropolitan

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Annotation: Today, public transport is distinguished from other industries by a highly competitive environment. Due to the strong competition, it is necessary to focus on the quality of services provided by public transport, including the transportation system of the Tashkent metro, to meet the needs of consumers according to the needs of the modern transport market, types of services, convenience in the process of using passenger transport services.

Key words: history, metro, development, communication, vehicles, above-ground.

Introduction

Tashkent transport system is one of the largest parts of the national and interstate communication networks. Currently, passenger vehicles in Tashkent are served by bus, directional Taxi, Taxi and Metropolitan view.

Providing comfortable and high-quality transport services to citizens of our country, ensuring the stable operation of transport and communication systems is important in the development of our state.

Tashkent Metro-ranks first in Central Asia in terms of the number of passengers transported, since 2021 under the Ministry of transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent Metro began to be built in 1968-1970. The first line, "Chilonzor", was commissioned in 1977. There are 17 stops on the "chilanzar" line, 11 on the "Uzbekistan" line, 8 on the "Yunusabad" line, and 7 on the "ring" line.

Tashkent Metro is located at a shallow level (depth 8-10m), and most of the inter-station tunnels are built in a closed way (through shielded drilling). Metropolitan structures were calculated to withstand a magnitude 9 earthquake on the MSK-64 scale, taking into account the high seismicity of the area.

For the 36th purpose of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022 PF-60 "new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2022-2026", it was established to "develop a unified transport system with continuous connection of all types of transport, to create the opportunity to reach

and return to the destination on the basis of daily transport The consistent implementation of these goals will be instrumental in building a new Uzbekistan.

1. Brief classification and new directions of the Tashkent Metro

On the basis of the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the implementation of the project for the construction of the Sergeli line of the Tashkent Metro" PQ-2664 dated November 29, 2016, work was carried out on the construction of the Sergeli line of the Tashkent Metro, as well as the second stage of the Yunusabad line and The Tashkent ring metro line.

Currently, 4 lines with a length of 92.8 km with 43 stations are in operation. The Sergeli line under construction on the Estakada type was completed in 2017-2021 with a length of 6.3 km. It should be noted that as a significant aspect of the project, the possibility of merging the most densely populated Sergeli district into a single urban transport network is envisaged. Also, the ring Metro under construction along the Tashkent ring highway is important in providing quality and fast transport services to the residents of the city of Tashkent. The total length of the ring Metro will be 54.8 km, consisting of 35 stations. This project is planned to be implemented in 5 stages.

Figure 1. Tashkent khalqa Metropolitan scheme

Existing and future indicators of the Tashkent Metro

№ п.п.	Metropolitan line	Length (km.)	Number of stops (PCs.)	Passenger flow (min.passenger. For 2017).
I.	Available			
1.	Chilonzor	15,5	12	36 206,8
2.	Uzbekistan	14,3	11	20 401,9
3.	Yunus-Abad (1-step)	6,4	6	4 989,4
	Total	36,2	29	61 598,1
II.	Under construction and design			
1.	Yunus-Abad (2-step)	3	2	
2.	Sergeli	6,3	5	
3.	Ring Metropolitan	54,8	35	
	Total	64,1	42	
	Total	100,3	71	

In 2017-2020, 11.2 km of estakada-type Metropolitan construction work was carried out on the first stage of the Tashkent khalqa metro in the direction of the "Dostlik" metro station and "Qo'yliq" market (2-3 pictures).

Figure 2. Tashkent khalqa Metropolitan line "Qo'yliq" station

Figure 3. Tashkent khalqa Metropolitan line - "Roxat" station

The project “construction of Phase 2 of the Yunusabad Metro” is one of the important factors in improving the infrastructure of the City metropolitan area. The tunnel section of the Metro was built in a closed way using the mechanized tunnel drilling complex "HERRENKNESHT AG" ((TPMK (tunnel-tunneling mechanized complex) brought from Germany (figures 4-5).’

*Figure 4. “HERRENKNESHT AG”
tunnel drilling mechanized complex*

*Figure 5. Yunusabad line
“Turkestan” station*

As a result of these creative works, it is worth noting the development of the urban ecosystem through the development of Tashkent into one of the largest megacities and the use of environmentally efficient vehicles.

Currently, a number of proposals are presented below in order to conveniently and safely organize the movement of vehicles in the city of Tashkent, to provide quality transport services to the population.

2. Project proposal for the construction of an above-ground ring metro line in Tashkent (monolithic method)

According to the 2018-2020 data of the international Metro Association, prices for the construction of 1 km of underground metro are indicated in the Cross-City Section. For example, in Europe, the Berlin U-Bahn is 1 km. for 250 million. US \$ 150 million for the metro of the city of St. Petersburg in the CIS. US \$ 45 million for the construction of the Delhi Metro in Asia. Costs in the amount of US dollars have gone.

Currently, new modern design and construction methods are being studied and new techniques and technologies are being used in the Uzbek metro and bridge industry, gradually abandoning the principles of default design and construction. One well – known and unconventional method is the monolithic method of construction. Monolithic construction is well developed in most developed countries of the world.

Figure 6. Modern monolithic road and bridges in Tashkent.

Monolithic construction is a method of building and transport structures, in which the main material of structures is monolithic reinforced concrete. The reinforced concrete structure is strong and long-lasting, and also has high performance. The main feature of monolithic construction is that the place for the production of material for monolithic bridges and other engineering structures is a construction site. The use of monolithic reinforced concrete makes it possible to implement various architectural forms, as well as reduce steel consumption by 7-20%, and concrete by up to 12%.

The city of Tashkent today is one of the largest megacities, the speed of movement and traffic flow increased by 2-3 times, and more than 700-800 thousand traffic moves on the streets of the city in one day. Thanks to this, the construction of road infrastructure facilities, transport facilities, including bridges, roadways and metropolitans, is developing in accordance with the demand of the Times.

The project of a road tunnel connecting Sergeli and Yakkasaroy districts was carried out in two stages. In the first stage, a nearly 2-kilometer track was completed from Chushanota Street to Tashkent Ring Road. A 788-meter bridge was built on its section that passed over the small ring road and two 207-meter crossings were built at its junction with the Tashkent Ring Road. (Figure 6).

As a continuation of the existing new construction work in our city, proposals have been developed for the implementation of the Tashkent ring surface Metro at Stage 2 using the monolithic method. For comparison, monolithic trestle and prefabricated reinforced concrete options were compared.

Price for 1km monolithic trestle – 15.7 million, dollar

When using prefabricated reinforced concrete structures in the traditional way, complications arise in the construction of curved plots. During construction,

it will be necessary to carry out many demolition and dismantling works.

Price for 1km – 13.5 million for prefabricated reinforced concrete trestle, dollar

The difference between the price of prefabricated reinforced concrete and monolithic trestle is 14%.

2. Stage 2 of construction of the above-ground khalqa Metro in Tashkent

In the city of Tashkent, at the 2nd stage of construction of the above-ground khalqa Metro, there is a plot of a number of problematic Trestles. In particular, the section from Station 11 to Station 14 is a problem area. It is currently built up to Station 12. Surface and underground options for the transfer of a metro line between stops 12-14 were considered.

The line will be 3.85 km long with 2 stops. The cost of the option in the relay is 77.8 million rubles. US dollars, the cost of the tunnel option is 89.4 million. US dollars. Respectively, the construction periods are -1 year and 3 months in the trestle variant and 2 years in the tunnel variant. In the Estacada variant, 1km. price received Rs. US dollars, 1km in the tunnel variant. price received Rs 23.2 crore. The cost is US dollars (price are indicated taking into account the values of all metropolitan structures and elements, engineering networks).

As a result of the comparison of economic indicators, the following technical and economic indicators were considered. First, the cost for demolition was estimated at 132 buildings and 263.7 crore in the Estacada variant. sum, 27 buildings in the tunnel variant and 35.7 crore. som.

Secondly, the cost for transplanting trees in the construction area is 312 trees and 10.3 billion in the Estacada option. sum, 93 trees in the tunnel variant and 1.9 crore. som.

Thirdly, the cost in the case of transportable engineering networks is 7.8 km in length and 23.8 billion in the Estacada variant of the transportable communications. the length of the Communications, which will be moved in the tunnel variant, will be 2.34 km and 10.3 billion. som.

The advantages of the trestle option are manifested in a relatively low total construction value and a short construction period.

As advantages of the tunnel option, it should be noted the low cost and ease of use in the operation process, the absence of external climatic influences on metropolitan systems and the low cost of moving trees and engineering networks.

The difference between the cost of surface and underground metro options is 15%.

In the underground variant, 13 and 14 stops are located underground.

Several design solutions of stations and tunnels were considered. In this, a comparative analysis of the options for traditional underground stops and modern

underground stops was carried out. In practice, one-column stations, two-column stations and domed stations are used in the Tashkent Metro. In most cases, these types of stops are built in an open way. Project proposed stops can be built in open or closed ways according to the conditions of the area. The proposed stops were designed with three domes and monolithic closures.

Economy by optimizing the construction of the station in this 27%
 14.1 from building materials%
 5.4 from the workforce%
 7.5% of the construction period.

4. Proposals to increase the length of the intermediate device

To determine the most rational variant of the trestle construction, the technical and economic indicators of each of the above-developed options are compared among themselves, and the most optimal option is determined.

In this tutorial, we will determine the cost of the construction of each option, compare them and choose the most optimal option. In this case, the size of the tread elements is determined for each option, and these volumes are multiplied by the unit price.

In the calculations, depending on the construction complexity of the trestle element, the amount of 1m³ of reinforced concrete spent on it is multiplied by its cost. For example, the unit price for 1 m³ of reinforced concrete, which is used for the construction of drill piles of the floor and rostverk, was accepted at the rate of 7,000,000 rubles, for the upper and lower parts of the base body, for head beams of 26.0 m, at the rate of 7,500,000 rubles. This unit prices are determined according to production estimates.

To determine the most rational variant of the Metro trestle structure, the cost of one kilometer of the trestle length was taken as the main indicator.

Constructs 1 km. comparative analysis of costs to go.

Intermediate device length	Number		Volume (m ³)		Estimated price (billion Soum).	
	Intermediate device	Base	Intermediate device	Base	Intermediate device	Base
26m	156	40	3370	5600	25,275	39,20
33m	120	30	3290	4200	24,675	29,40
42m	96	25	2590	3500	19,425	24,50

**The possibility of extending the range by about 1.5 times;*

**Concrete consumption for 1 balcony – 27,41m³*

As can be seen from the comparative table, inside the trestle options, the lowest figure of the total price of construction was given 3 options. According to this option, the value determined according to the volume of reinforced concrete (i.e. – the volume of work) spent on the construction of 42 m of estacada was 43,925,000,000, and 1 pog/meter of price was 43,925,000. Elements applied (option 1) 1 pog/meter price of Estacada is 64,475,000. This is an indicator that is almost 1.5 times larger than the selected option value.

In the case of 1 pog/meter price of Estacada, we can also take 3 options as the most rational option.

Thus, it was proved that the structure with the height of its supports on the metro trestle solution is 6-7 meters, and the length of the intermediate device is 42.0 meters.

Conclusion

1.The use of monolithic reinforced concrete makes it possible to implement various architectural forms, as well as reduce steel consumption by 7-20%, and concrete by up to 12%.

2.1km price for monolithic metro Estacada – 15.7 million. dollar, 1km for prefabricated reinforced concrete trestle – 13.5 million. dollars. The difference between prefabricated reinforced concrete and monolithic trestle price is 14%.

3.In Tashkent, it is advisable to design and build a plot of a number of problematic Trestles existing at Stage 2 of the construction of the above-ground ring Metro in the form of an underground Metro Tunnel. In order to find a scientifically based solution to current issues in these problematic area, the base doctoral student of the Department "bridges and tunnels" of the Tashkent State transport University Sh.Sh. Kadirova is carrying out the final stage of his scientific work on the topic" Improving the competitiveness of the Tashkent metropolitan area". In the scientific work, practical recommendations are being developed on the rationality of the use of an underground metro in problem areas in the construction of a ring Metro.

4.At the 2nd stage of construction of the above-ground ring Metro in Tashkent, the difference between the cost of the above-ground and underground metro options is 15%.

5.In the construction of the underground metro, a concept of new metro station structures of modern appearance is proposed. The use of new type underground metro stations is considered and economically efficient compared to traditional metro stations.

6.Among the recommendations for increasing the length of the intermediate

device for use in areas where it is advisable to build the metropolitan area in the form of a trestle, the 42-meter intermediate device is the most rational. This allows you to extend the length of the intermediate device by about 1.5 times.

7. In order to systematically develop the above proposals, the Department of bridges and tunnels continues its scientific and innovative activities at an accelerated pace.

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